

A Study on Awareness Towards Environmental Sustenance and Ecofriendly Entrepreneurial Projects

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Abstract

Environment sustenance is a talk of all the leaders at the global level, so also with India. Awareness is created among masses regarding the protection of environment, becoming self-sufficient, recycling of resources, preservation of wild life are some of the topic discussed and debated. All though there is buzz word of environment sustenance many of the projects by the government do not promote protection for the environment. Festivals are popular among Indians and Deepavali is one such festival of lights, rather people assume it is festival of bursting crackers. For the research study data is collected from the families residing in Bangalore and their experience in celebration the festival and also awareness about of environment pollution. The major objective is to understand the mindset during the festival time and whether they are aware the consequences experienced after bursting of crackers. The study has concluded that majority of the respondents were aware of environment pollution and hence resented from buying crackers during this year's deepavali celebrations. The suggestion is also provided to protect environment, being self-sufficient, adopt recycle methods and transform the economy by setting up entrepreneurial ventures which deal with eco-friendly products that are generally manufactured and marketed by women entrepreneurs.

Keywords: Sustainable development, ecofriendly ventures, entrepreneurial activity, Environment protection.

Introduction

Sustainability is the ability to continue a defined behavior indefinitely. The environment in which we are surviving need to have sustainable development and leading to sustainable economic growth. While reading about the tragedy of the commons which was developed by ecologist and philosopher Garret Hardin (1968). It was observed: “the damage that innocent actions by individuals can inflict on the environment”

Environment sustainability includes

1. Shift towards renewable resources and limiting the consumption of nonrenewable resources.

2. Protect health of ecosystems by avoiding ecosystems becoming irreparably damaged.
3. Avoiding excess of pollution either in the form of noise, air or any other type of pollution which will damage the health of people and other species.
4. Target welfare of the people both economic and social welfare and not concern of increasing Gross domestic product, per capita income at the cost of the resources being depleted.
5. Integration of economic decisions which have an impact on the long run and are caused due to unplanned activities of today.

In the year 1990 Herman Daly, one of the early pioneers of ecological sustainability proposed that

1. For renewable resources, the rate of harvest should not exceed the rate of regeneration (sustainable yield)
2. For pollution, the rates of waste generation from projects should not exceed the assimilative capacity of the environment (sustainable waste disposal); and
3. For nonrenewable resources the depletion of the nonrenewable resources should require comparable development of renewable substitutes for that resource.

Environmental sustainability is the rates of renewable resource harvest, pollution creation, and non-renewable resource depletion that can be continued indefinitely. One of the greatest issue seen today is the generation after generation are violating the law of protecting the environment. In India, we are conscious about the way we behave towards the environment. In some cases, we are only propagating the idea of protection but not practicing in actuals. In today's world, protection and preservation is very important and worrying about the destruction.

Pollution and Effect on the People

The crux of the study through this paper is seen during the festival season of Deepavali. As the festival like deepavali approaches how people can reduce the usage of fireworks. They cause extensive air pollution in a very short amount period. Once these crackers are burst out there will be toxins in the air, harmful chemical smoke is left in the air. People with the breathing problems find it difficult to sustain as they fall short of breath, asthma, attacks become frequent and people will be prone to new types of diseases.

Colouring agent in the crackers has lithium which is red, copper blue, strontium red, barium nitrate green, antimony sulphide is glitter. There is more effect on the skin and wart formation. Lung, respiratory problem occur hormonal imbalances and muscular weakens seen during this period of inhaling the smoke. There is element fuel which is potassium nitrate which causes toxic dust and lung cancer. These chemical join the waters flowing and affect the vegetation too.

Review of literature

According to Vignesh Radhakrishnan, bursting of crackers causes particular matter of pollution, crackers contains several chemical which produce different colours and effect. These chemicals affect human beings both infants and adults.

According to ShikhaGoyal fire crackers on Diwali are some or the other way responsible for air pollution. It is better to go for green crackers to reduce pollution

Objectives of the Study

1. To understand the concept of environment sustenance and the approach by the people.
2. To analyze and evaluate the pollution raised due the festive celebrations in Bangalore.
3. To suggest & support ecofriendly products started by women entrepreneurs for the festive season.

Methodology

Data Collection

Primary data is collected through the questionnaire prepared and distributed to the families residing in Bangalore. Secondary data is collected through the books, magazines and blog of prominent writers.

Data Analysis

The collected data is tabulated and pictorial representation is done as a part of data analysis. Each question is interpreted and suggestions are provided.

Data Analysis

1. Gender of Respondents

Source: Primary data

Out of 243 respondents 96 of them are female i.e. 40% and 147 are male i.e. 60%.

2. Celebrated the festival of Deepavali this Year

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: Among 243 respondents 53 respondents have not celebrated the Deepavali festival this year and 190 respondents celebrated the festival. 21.81% among the respondents did not celebrate and 78.19% celebrated the festival.

3. Purchase of Crackers

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: 89% of the respondents have not bought crackers to celebrate the festival and 11% of the respondents have bought crackers to celebrate the festival this year. 27 respondents have bought crackers and celebrated the Deepavali festival and 216 respondents celebrated without crackers.

4. Amount Spent on the Crackers

Amount spent	Number of Respondents
Less than Rs. 500	11
Rs. 501 to Rs. 2000	10
Above Rs.2000	6
Total	27

Source : Primary Data

Interpretation: Out of 27 respondents 11 respondents spent less than Rs 500 i.e. 40.74 %, 10 respondents spent Rs. 501 to Rs. 2000 i.e. 37.04 % and 6 respondents spent above Rs 2000 i.e. 22.22 % to purchase crackers.

5. Motive Behind Buying Crackers

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: Among 216 respondents 2 families i.e. 0.92% were sick during the festival because of which crackers were avoided by them, 97 of them i.e. 44.90% are not interested in burning crackers, 3 respondents i.e. 1.388% couldn’t buy crackers as they were busy and had no time, 5 respondents i.e. 2.31% were out of station during the festival due to which purchase of crackers were not possible and major part 109 respondents i.e. 50.46% didn’t buy the crackers as it pollutes the environment.

6. Crackers cause Noise and Air Pollution

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: 234 respondents among the 243 respondents are aware of the bursting crackers will generate noise and air pollution but 9 respondents are not aware that bursting crackers will generate noise and air pollution i.e. 3.70% of respondents unaware of crackers generating noise and air pollution and 96.29% have knowledge about that the bursting crackers will generate noise and air pollution.

Findings

- Through survey it was found that 40% of the respondents are female and 60% are male.
- In Bangalore during the festive season who have celebrated Deepavali with lot of pomp and splendor. However, among the respondents 21.81% they did not celebrate the Deepavali festival while 78.19% celebrated the festival this year.
- We were also surprised to see among the families who have responded 89% of the respondents have not bought crackers to celebrate the Deepavali and only a scanty 11% of the respondents have bought crackers to celebrate the festival this year.
- Among the 11% of respondents who spent money in buying crackers only 40.74% respondents spent less than Rs 500 as cost in buying crackers. While, 37.04 % respondents spent Rs. 501 to Rs.2000 and 22.22% respondents spent above Rs.2000 in purchasing crackers for Deepavali festival.
- The research went ahead to find the reason for not celebrating the festival , 0.92% were sick during the festival, While 44.90% are not interested in burning crackers, similarly 1.388% were busy and had no time, 2.31% were out of station and major part i.e. 50.46% didn't buy the crackers as it pollutes the environment.
- There was a question whether the crackers pollute environment and 96.29% of the respondents were aware of polluting generated through bursting crackers and 3.70% of the respondents are not aware of air and noise pollution caused due to burning of crackers.
- In spite of 96.29% of the crowd is aware of the harm and negative effect of the bursting crackers people try to pollute more by bursting crackers.

Suggestions

1. Ways and Means to Maintain Eco Friendliness

Natural air and green plantations to flourish inside and outside buildings The buildings are thermally insulated which keeps the temperature lower in summers and higher in winters, thereby reducing.

Network of rain harvesting systems ensure continuous recharging of ground water table. The sewage treatment plant recycles the water filtered through its beds for use of horticulture, green lawns, hedges and plantations of college. Conservation of electricity is ensured by its usage only when and where needed. Slowly a culture has been built amongst faculty and staff to put off appliances, lights and fans when they leave. Separate agency with specialized expertise and dealing in waste collection and disposal has been hired to collect the wastes on daily basis.

2. Glimpses from Women Entrepreneurs

Women entrepreneurs are moving across the society with numerous products made out of scrap, recycled or easily available natural resources. The green options are available where in market players can tap an environmentally friendly customer base.

The owner Kanchan Rana of Green The Gap selling eco-friendly products says that they have launched the wax project this Diwali, wherein, they are bringing out eco-friendly candles made by the under-privileged mothers of Jagadamba camp slum in South Delhi. Up cycled and molten candles are made by them out of waste materials.

Neha Pradhan Arora, Head of Programmes, Sweccha, and Delhi-based environmental NGO Greener products are expensive for the Indian market that is generally price driven. But opting for a greener option is more of a mindset, than anything else. She tells that if one can shell out a huge sum for a movie in a multiplex or a brand, then people need to know that most of the eco-friendly products are premium products. A lot of hand work goes into the making of such products that contributes to the high pricing. She adds that, “We register more sales for the green products on our websites than the physical stores”.

Conclusion

Environment protections are the must and should be priority from the people. The government should take initiative; entrepreneurs should look into the prospects of producing ecofriendly products which can be easily destroyed without much damage to surrounding. All species are inter-dependended hence damaging or polluting water, land or air will hamper the growth of animals, birds, plants. Creating awareness among the masses is essential thereby we are protecting the environment for future generations

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